

Exam Script Verification System Using Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract-- The process of manually verifying exam scripts is time-consuming, error-prone, and often lacks consistency, particularly in Nigerian educational institutions. This study proposes an innovative exam script verification system that utilizes artificial intelligence (AI) techniques to automate and improve the efficiency of the verification process. The research aims to enhance the accuracy and reliability of grading by leveraging AI algorithms for evaluating exam scripts. The system employs machine learning models to analyze and assess various aspects of the scripts, including content, structure, and coherence. By training the AI models on a large dataset of annotated scripts, the system learns to identify common errors, provide feedback on areas of improvement, and generate standardized grades. The proposed system takes into account the unique challenges and requirements of the Nigerian educational context, including diverse curricula, large student populations, and limited resources. Through rigorous testing and evaluation, the effectiveness and performance of the system are assessed, comparing it with traditional manual grading methods. The outcomes of this research have the potential to revolutionize the exam grading process in Nigerian educational institutions, leading to increased efficiency, fairness, and accuracy in assessing student performance.

Keywords-- Artificial intelligence, verification system, Exam scripts, education system

I. INTRODUCTION

Prior to 1977, various forms of examination malpractice were already prevalent. However, the situation escalated in the early 1970s with widespread cheating occurring in the WAEC examination, leading to a national problem that affected educational institutions from primary schools to tertiary level. The year 1977 marked a significant turning point in the history of examinations in Nigeria when the West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) became the sole authority responsible for conducting public examinations in the country (Deepti et al., 2015).

In response to the growing concerns regarding the conduct of examinations and the timely release of results, a judicial commission of inquiry was established to investigate the affairs of WAEC. The commission recognized the excessive workload placed on WAEC and made recommendations to alleviate the burden, including the establishment of additional examination bodies to distribute the workload. Another issue contributing to examination malpractice was the practice of school principals registering more candidates than their facilities could accommodate. This overcrowding made effective supervision challenging as candidates were crammed into limited spaces (Gatos et al., 2006).

Reports highlighted situations where schools registered 200 candidates despite having halls that could accommodate them. In such cases, supervisors would be assigned to one class, leaving other classrooms unattended and facilitating cheating through dictation (Ojerinde, 2004). Candidates would also bring in materials to assist them during exams, resorting to copying information on small sheets of paper hidden in shoes or writing on concealed parts of their bodies.

These practices illustrate the extent of examination malpractice and the challenges faced by educational institutions in Nigeria. Efforts to combat this issue are crucial to uphold the integrity of examinations and ensure fair evaluation of students' knowledge and abilities.

Despite the ongoing efforts to address malpractice in Nigerian schools and institutions, the prevalence of such misconduct continues to rise, posing a significant threat to the academic system. It has permeated various forms, with impersonation emerging as a prominent issue. Numerous instances have been reported where individuals are hired to write exams on behalf of others. This form of cheating represents the highest level of academic dishonesty and demands absolute eradication (Deepti et al., 2015).

In response to this pressing challenge, this study introduces a software-based approach aimed at validating exam scripts. The proposed method involves analyzing handwritten characters from the query script and comparing them with those found in other documents handwritten by the suspect. This verification process seeks to ascertain the authenticity of suspected scripts, providing an effective means to detect and address potential instances of fraud.

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II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The study conducted by Makoju et al. (2004) investigated the perspectives of parents and secondary school teachers regarding the factors contributing to examination malpractice in Nigeria. According to the responses from parents, one of the key factors encouraging malpractice is the perceived disconnect between examination questions and the syllabus. Parents argue that when questions deviate from the prescribed syllabus, it creates an environment conducive to malpractice. The teaching syllabus, developed by the Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC), should ideally provide a common scope of knowledge. However, concerns have been raised that the syllabus for the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB) exams is excessively burdensome and challenging for candidates, leading to difficulties in coping (Makoju et al., 2004).

Another factor highlighted by parents is the use of objective questions, which are believed to facilitate malpractice. Students have developed techniques for covertly sharing answers through subtle finger movements during objective tests. In the same study, secondary school teachers were also surveyed about the factors responsible for malpractice. Among the 1685 teachers surveyed, 879 (52.17%) expressed the view that students lack readiness to learn. In many public schools, students are frequently observed loitering on the streets, playing video games, or engaging in recreational activities instead of dedicating themselves to their studies. Consequently, when examinations approach, these unprepared students resort to malpractice. Other factors identified as contributing to examination malpractice include the overemphasis on paper qualifications, the intense desire of parents for their children to pass at any cost, and the conduct of supervisors and custodians of examination papers, who often mirror the wider societal challenges.

The excessive emphasis on paper qualifications is a strong catalyst for malpractice. As long as paper qualifications remain the primary focus rather than practical skills that enable individuals to effectively function in society, the issue of malpractice will persist. The obsession with paper qualifications stems from the inadequate implementation of the National Policy on Education. Efforts are gradually shifting from the acquisition of paper credentials towards the demonstration of practical skills and academic excellence. Possessing paper qualifications without substantial practical experience to support them will eventually lose significance (Chandan, 2014).

A. Instances and Types of Examination Malpractice

Before 1977, various forms of examination malpractice had already been observed. However, since the early 1970s, when widespread cheating first occurred in the West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) exams, it has escalated into a nationwide problem, spanning from primary schools to tertiary institutions. In 1977, a significant turning point in Nigeria's examination history took place when the WAEC, the sole body responsible for

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conducting public exams at that level, faced scrutiny through a judicial commission of inquiry. The purpose was to address issues related to the efficient administration of examinations and the timely release of results (Makoju et al., 2004).

The commission acknowledged the excessive workload burdening the WAEC and made recommendations to alleviate this issue, including the establishment of additional examination bodies to share the workload. Another contributing factor to examination malpractice is the excessive registration of candidates beyond the available facilities in schools, which some school principals employ as a means to facilitate malpractice. The limited resources and the abundance of candidates create significant challenges for effective supervision, as many candidates are crammed into a single examination hall. There have been reports of situations where 200 candidates were registered in a school with halls capable of accommodating them, but due to poor arrangement, dictation would occur in separate classrooms when supervisors were positioned far apart (Ojerinde, 2004).

During examinations, candidates may attempt to bring in materials that they believe will aid them in answering the questions. This form of malpractice often involves copying information onto small sheets of paper, similar in size to complementary cards, which can be hidden in shoes or mathematical sets. Additionally, information may be written on concealed parts of the body (Ojerinde, 2004).

B. Efforts Made to Combat Examination Malpractice

Various entities, including examination bodies, governmental bodies at the federal, state, and local levels, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and individuals, have adopted different approaches in their endeavors to address examination malpractice. An illustrative example is the headcount conducted in Oyo State, where the Commissioner for Education assembled a team to visit schools and determine the number of students in each institution, aiming to prevent malpractice. The West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) has also launched public campaigns to raise awareness about the consequences of malpractice and the corresponding penalties, employing tools such as handbills, posters, jingles, seminars, and workshops. The National Examinations Council (NECO) has conducted workshops, seminars, and public enlightenment campaigns. Additionally, an NGO called the Exam Ethics Project has devoted considerable efforts to combatting examination malpractice.

Individuals like Jegede (2003) have also taken initiatives to address these issues. Furthermore, the federal government has enacted legislation prohibiting examination malpractice, with the most recent example being the introduction of computer-based examinations by the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB) as a measure to curb malpractice.

C. Implications of Examination Malpractices

As highlighted by Ija'iya (2001), examination malpractice is indicative of a decline in the quality of education. This suggests that the overall educational standards in Nigeria are compromised, as malpractice incidents permeate throughout the country. Consequently, this detrimental situation can have adverse effects on national development. Furthermore, individuals who engage in cheating at lower educational levels are more likely to persist in such behaviors as they progress to higher levels of education. Upon entering society after graduation, these individuals' previous attitudes may easily lead them to engage in corrupt practices.

Another significant consequence is that individuals who obtain certificates through dishonest means may use those credentials to secure positions for which they are unqualified. This ultimately results in poor performance and reduced productivity. Consequently, the development and utilization of both human and material resources become jeopardized. Instances have arisen in which students face suspension, examiners are blacklisted, and schools lose recognition as examination centers due to various forms of malpractice. These measures are intended to serve as deterrents to others contemplating similar actions.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN METHODOLOGY AND RESULT ANALYSIS

A. Methodology for PRMS Development

In developing the PRMS (Practitioner Registration Management System), we opted to utilize the iterative waterfall model as our system development life cycle (SDLC) approach. This model entails a sequential progression through various stages, including requirement definition, system and software design, implementation and unit testing, integration and system testing, and operational maintenance. Additionally, we incorporated elements from other models, such as prototyping, to facilitate system definition and analysis, as well as the creation of data flow diagrams to depict data flow within the system.

B. Reasons for Choosing the Waterfall Model

The decision to employ the iterative waterfall model was driven by its ability to divide the system development lifecycle into distinct phases. Each phase entails well-defined activities, allowing for a focused approach to system development. For example, during the Analysis stage, we conducted structured analysis to thoroughly examine the system's data flow functionality and graphical structure. Subsequently, this analysis informed the software design phase, where we devised the software architecture to decompose the system into modules and

establish relationships among them. Furthermore, we designed appropriate data structures and algorithms for the modules.

After an exhaustive review of some methods adopted in the development of the existing system we choose to develop a new system that will recognize scripts using unsupervised machine learning technique.

C. Benefits of the proposed system

Benefit of the new proposed system includes the following:

- a) Help check exam impersonation and malpractice
- b) Reduce cost of employing many human personnel
- c) Easy to use and integrate in the society
- d) Easily adaptable to other image processing systems

D. Justification of the proposed system

Having proposed the new system this section outlines the fundamental reasons why this work should be accepted and problems this project will address in the public domain:

- i. Even though the cost of implementing the new system might be a little higher than the conventional system, the benefits on a long run will outweigh the high cost. This is because of its simple, easy to use interface structure design.
- ii. This work has vast application such as automobile, space, industrial e.t.c

E. The Organization

The proposed project will be guided by the aforementioned objectives and other necessary universal modeling languages and equations where required.

Figure 2: Dataflow diagram

F. Inputs to the system

This section describes all the necessary input to the system. The software input includes the number of new captured exam script images to be analyzed and lots more

G. Output of the system

Figure 3: flow chart for output of the system

H. Procedure and processes

- **Image Acquisition:** this process involves capturing the real and query document using a scanner, HD camera or any image acquisition device.
- **Image pre-processing:** this step is a preliminary image processing step to get a better image quality using histogram equalization. this technique reduces background noise from the scanned optical character document.

- **Image Binarization:** this process converts the captured image into a bi-level (black and white color) in preparation for processing.
- **Digital segmentation:** this is an image processing technique for finding the boundary of an object within image. We use this to locate characters in the both documents to be recognized using both line and character segmentation techniques.
- **Image Normalization:** this procedure not only removes noise from the image but also bring the image to a range of intensity value that is normal for feature extraction process.
- **Training:** The putative match analysis is constructed using what called a relative polar matrix (RPM) to create a vector with the query and real script document from each pair of coincide inliers. A match will yield vector with equal angle close to equal relative length and cosine angle while false match on the other hand will yield varying cosines and lengths. The relative length of these vectors v_a and v_b is presented below:

$$R = \frac{\min(\|v_a\|, \|v_b\|)}{\max(\|v_a\|, \|v_b\|)} \quad - \quad - \quad (1)$$

From the equation (1) both the cosine of the angle: θ between vectors and relative length: R will always be in the interval $[-1, .1]$ and $[0, .1]$ respectively. The first column of the matrix contains results for first match and each row contains the pairs of (R, θ) to each pair of matches. Those that are true inliers will yield similar values of (R, θ) even if the images have different rotation and scale. However, false matches will yield pairs of (R, θ) that have different values also when a false match coincide, all putative matches will yield quite different values of (R, θ) . This process is repeated continuously hence the second column will contain the pairs relative to this match and so on. As show in figure 3 (matching of two documents), the method finds the corresponding matching points using the yellow outliners even for extreme situation. In a case where one symmetrical matrix is involved for both (R) and (θ) in the RPM matrix, there is just one outlier giving a clear trace in the matrices. According to since both (R) and (θ) are symmetric, all the information could be packed into one matrix as the diagonal contains no information as the points cannot be compared to themselves.

Figure 3: feature of extracted images of scripts

Figure 4: sample of captured handwritten exam script

Figure 5: sample of input document (handwritten)

I. Output form design

Figure 6: framework for matched document

Figure 7: framework for Rejected documents

IV. PROGRAM MODULE SPECIFICATION

The model are divided into sections such as the sensing and image acquisition section, processing and training section, the robot odometry and the trajectory modules.

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A. Program flow chart

Figure 8: system flow chart

B. Authentication Test Data:

The test data for authentication consists of a new username and password. The system will validate this data to authenticate the user.

C. Hardware Device Test:

This test ensures that the system can access connected hardware devices such as keyboards for input and system units for processing.

D. Database System Test:

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During this test, various data, including extracted data and instant tables created at runtime, will be stored in the database. The connectivity path will also be used as test data.

E. System Integration and Testing:

Before deployment, the system's operability is checked through a series of planned and systematic test methods. The proposed system is tested in parallel with the software, which includes analysis, implementation, and maintenance phases. The testing procedures involved in the software development life cycle are unit testing, integration testing, module testing, and acceptance testing.

F. System Conversion:

System conversion involves converting the existing methods and models into the new system by implementing the necessary software and hardware tools for its operability.

G. Documentation:

Documentation is a crucial part of system development as it ensures future maintenance. The researcher has thoroughly documented the entire system, including organizing the source code and providing comments to explain each section. This documentation will assist software engineers, programmers, and system analysts

This research introduces a digital approach for verifying examination scripts. The motivation behind this development stems from the prevalence of exam impersonation, malpractice, and concerns raised by lecturers regarding handwriting inconsistencies or unusually high scores from notorious and unserious students who exploit their knowledge of the system. These issues have posed significant challenges for institutions in terms of detection and investigation. In light of previous studies, this work proposes a novel system that utilizes artificial intelligence to rectify and authenticate potentially questionable documents.

I. Conclusion

The alarming production of underqualified graduates in our country necessitates the implementation of effective detection mechanisms to identify and discipline unserious students in higher institutions before their negative influence permeates the academic environment and the nation as a whole. To address the problem of detecting examination fraudsters in higher institutions, we propose modeling and simulating an image processing fraud

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detection system using optical sensors. This approach involves characterizing students' behaviors during examinations, creating a comprehensive database of all students in the institution, developing a rule-based system to monitor fraudulent activities, and designing an intelligent system for validating suspicious examination scripts.

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